

STUDIES IN ORGANO-ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART IX. SYNTHESIS OF ARSENIC ANALOGUE OF SUCCINIMIDE

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Arsenic analogue of succinimide has been synthesised by the application of Fittig's reaction to a mixture of succinyl chloride and phenyldichloroarsine in xylene solution. The constitution of the succinylphenylarsine has been established by its reduction to phenylcyclo-tetramethylenearsine and the formation of HgCl_2 -double salt and arsonium derivative.

This paper deals with the synthesis of the arsenic analogue (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) of succinimide, which could not be prepared from succinic anhydride and arsine. A phenyl derivative (I, $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$) of the desired arsine has, however, been prepared by Fittig's reaction from succinyl chloride and phenyldichloroarsine.

Arseno-magnesium compound of the type $\text{AsC}_6\text{H}_5(\text{MgBr})_2$ is transformed in benzene solution by acetyl chloride into diacetylphenylarsine, $\text{AsC}_6\text{H}_5(\text{COCH}_3)_2$, a yellow oil, which is oxidised in air and reacts with methyl iodide to form phenyltrimethylarsonium iodide and acetyl iodide. But carbonyl chloride or ethylene dibromide gives unstable compounds, which decompose, yielding arsenobenzene and carbon monoxide in the first case and arsenobenzene and ethylene in the second case (Job and Reich, *Compt. rend.*, 1923, 177, 56; Job, Reich and Vergnand, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1924, 38, 1404).

Similarly diphenylarsine reacts vigorously with acetyl chloride in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide to form diphenylacetylarsine (Steinkopf Schubart and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 678). The product decomposes on exposure to air and moisture with evolution of heat.

In the present investigation a mixture of succinyl chloride and phenyldichloroarsine was heated with sodium in dry xylene, containing a few c.c. of dry ethyl acetate. The condensation takes place in the following way :

The compound is very unstable as it readily undergoes hydrolysis to succinic acid and phenylarsenious oxide by atmospheric moisture; hence moisture was excluded in its preparation. It has a very corrosive effect on the skin.

The formula (I) was assigned to succinylphenylarsine on the following grounds :

- (i) It could be hydrolysed to succinic acid and phenylarsenious oxide.
- (ii) It could be reduced to the known phenylcyclo-tetramethylenearsenine.
- (iii) The m.p. and mixed m.p. of the methiodide and mercurichloride of Gruttner and Krause's product (*Ber.*, 1916, 41, 437) being identical with the same derivatives of the reduction product. The reduction of (I) was effected by sodium and absolute alcohol in toluene solution using the method of Stanley and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1515).

The compound (II) gives a mercuric chloride double salt and arsonium derivatives with alkyl iodides, the 5-membered ring remaining intact, (contrast the action of methyl iodide on diacetylphenylarsine).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Succinylphenylarsine — Dry benzene (50 c.c.), sodium wire (9 g.) and dry ethyl acetate (5 c.c.) were taken in a flask, provided with condenser and calcium chloride guard tube and kept for 1 hour. A mixture of succinyl chloride (freshly distilled, 15 g.) and phenyldichloroarsine (22 g.) was then introduced and the reaction started by heat after which the source of heat was withdrawn. The colour of the reaction mixture gradually changed to brown and after the abatement of the initial vigorous reaction the whole was heated for 1 hour on the steam-bath and then kept overnight. The highly viscous product was extracted several times with benzene, filtered till the filtrate was colourless, avoiding the access of moisture. After the removal of the solvent in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide, the residual brown oil was fractionated. The portion boiling at 116-20°/10 mm. was redistilled at 119-20°/10 mm. The oil is soluble in the ordinary organic solvents and gives a picrate, m.p. 117°. [Found: C, 50.9; H, 3.9; As, 31.8;

M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 230.9. $C_{10}H_9O_2As$ requires C, 50.8; H, 3.8; As, 31.7 per cent. M. W., 236].

Mercurichloride compound (I, $HgCl_2$) was prepared by mixing equimolecular proportion of the two in ether when a white precipitate was obtained. The substance was crystallised from hot alcohol, m.p. 245°. (Found: Hg, 39.4. $C_{10}H_9O_2AsCl_2Hg$ requires Hg, 39.4 per cent).

The Methiodide was prepared by heating in a sealed tube a mixture of succinylphenylarsine and 3 times its volume of methyl iodide for 10 hours at 100°. The resulting brown solution was freed from methyl iodide and the residual pasty oil was dissolved in alcohol and poured on to well cooled ether. The precipitated yellow solid was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 176°. (Found: As, 19.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2IAs$ requires As, 19.8 per cent).

The ethiodide was prepared in a similar manner with ethyl iodide, m.p. 165-67°. (Found: As, 18.9. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2AsI$ requires As, 19.1 per cent).

Reduction of Succinylphenylarsine to Phenylcyclotetramethylene-arsine.—A mixture of dry toluene (50 c.c.) and sodium (10 g.) was taken in a three-necked flask, fitted with a separating funnel, a mechanical stirrer and a condenser. The mixture was heated till the sodium melted and then the stirrer was set in motion so that the sodium was granular. The mixture of absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) and succinylphenylarsine was then run in and the whole agitated. A second lot of alcohol (25 c.c.) was again added and the mixture stirred till the sodium disappeared. The reaction was completed by heating and the cold reaction mass treated with water and the toluene layer washed successively with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, dilute alkali and finally with water. This was kept overnight with calcium chloride and filtered avoiding as far as possible moisture from the air, since the product decomposes in presence of water when it is distilled. After the removal of the solvent in *vacuo* the residual oil was fractionated, the portion distilling at 120-30°/15 mm. being collected. This was redistilled at 125-30°/15 mm. (Found: As, 36.2. $C_{10}H_{13}As$ requires As, 36.05 per cent).

Methyl cyclotetramethylenephunylarsonium iodide was prepared by the method of Gruttner and Krause (*loc. cit.*), m.p. and mixed m.p. 135-36°. (Found: As, 21.1. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{16}AsI$: As, 21.4 per cent).

Mercurichloride salt, prepared in a similar way, had m.p. and mixed m.p. with Gruttner and Krause's product, 160-62°.